

Psychological aspects of menopause

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Abstract

Menopause is the individual experience, proceeds differently in each of them. Some of them passed through this stage in a gentle manner, almost imperceptible to themselves and the environment. For the rest is a phenomenon almost traumatic effect associated with many ailments biopsychosocial nature. Important at this time it turns out that the mental approach the same woman, lifestyle, obtained support from family as well as the understanding that ends a phase of life begins again but that may be just as happy.

Keywords: menopause, stress depression, quality of life

Menopause is the next stage in a woman's life, situated between procreation and the aging of the organism. Associated with the cessation of gonadal function and cessation of menstruation. Changes include the cessation of ovarian synthesis of estrogen and progesterone and transformations occurring translate into quality of life of women in terms of life biopsychosocial [1].

In the course of menopause can be divided into the following periods:

- Premenopause - which is a period between a full fertility and menopausal women.

Frequently there are about 40 year old woman. In laboratory studies found the increased levels of pituitary gonadotropins (FSH) but subjectively woman can observe the lengthening or shortening cycles [1];

- Perimenopause - perimenopausal period beginning a few years before and ending 12 months after menopause. This applies mainly to the fifth decade of life. Laboratory states to lower levels of estrogen and progesterone and increased levels of pituitary gonadotropins (FSH and LH). In the ovary decreases the number of bubbles Graff, reduced the amount of gonadotropin receptors, disappears sensitivity of the ovaries to stimulate the pituitary.

Subjectively woman can follow menopausal symptoms, prolonged heavy bleeding and shortening cycle [1];

- Menopause - meaning the last menstrual bleeding. Inducing factor is decreasing in the ovaries number of follicles. What is important is lifestyle: stress, smoking, poor diet, estrogen-lowering drugs, diseases of the immune system, diabetes, chemotherapy, removal of the ovaries [1].

- Postmenopause - life of women following the menopause. At this time, there are physiological bleeding. In laboratory studies found high levels of FSH and LH and a significant decrease in levels of estrogen and progesterone [1].

There are also:

- *Artificial menopause* - caused by the expiry of ovarian function after surgery for their removal, followed by chemotherapy or radiation, dysfunction of the pituitary gland or very poor health (anorexia nervosa) [1].

- Premature menopause - following 40 years of age [1].

Menopause is the time which is assessed by women experience as a pejorative. Is seen in terms of deep losses associated with the loss of the role of maternal, youth and beauty. This loss is felt as an injustice that leads to the loss of meaning in life [2,3].

Perceived decline in the quality of life is also the result of low mood, irritability, headache, weakness, increased anxiety and worsening depression, as well as changing attitudes to their own femininity [4,5].

The woman is experiencing anxiety associated with a lack of understanding on the part of the partner,

people coming too.

As a result of the changes occurring on the physical level may arise distorted self-image, and mood swings and depressive tendencies may enhance physical ailments. As the third woman's life falls on the postmenopausal period, you should properly prepare for it.

It is a time of numerous threats, while increasing the probability of the incidence of coronary heart disease, diabetes, osteoporosis. There are problems in the sexual cohabitation and are associated with a decrease in estrogen levels. There is vaginal dryness, pain, and disorders of libido.

Menopause is the time, when the woman's body occur a number of hormonal changes. As a result, a woman suffers mood swings, problems with concentration, memory disorders and depression [6].

Appear unreasonable fears, lack of interest in sex, difficulty with sexual arousal, problems with sexual arousal, orgasm, and pain during sexual intercourse and lack of satisfaction with intercourse is only a matter of time [7].

As reported by literature depression during the climacteric they are diagnosed in approximately 50% of women [8]. It is believed that the risk of a depressive episode is two times higher in women than in men [9].

Studies show that there is a group of factors lowering the mood during menopause. According to Santoro and others [6]. These include history of depression, stressful life experiences, insomnia, lack of social support, cigarette smoking, elevated BMI, younger age, as well as belonging to African-Americans.

Geerlings and others [10] argue that depression may presage cognitive decline. Studies show that the use of hormone replacement therapy to improve cognitive function. The quality of verbal memory HRT following the onset of menopausal symptoms was significantly higher compared to women who started treatment with HRT after menopause [11].

As defined by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders major depressive episode is defined as the presence of 5 or more of the following symptoms persisting for most of the day almost every day for at least two consecutive weeks.

At least one of the symptoms must be depressed mood or loss of interest or experience pleasure [6, p.14].

With the diagnosis of depression is based on:

- depressed mood,
- loss of interest or pleasure of feeling on all forms of activity, or most of them,
- excessive sleepiness or insomnia,
- psychomotor retardation or agitation,
- a significant decrease or increase in body

weight,

- decrease or increase in appetite.
- fatigue or decrease in energy,
- impaired concentration, thinking,
- the problem of decision-making,
- thoughts about their worthlessness,
- inadequate or excessive guilt,
- recurrent thoughts of death,
- thoughts or suicide attempts [6, p.14].

As research in the development of depression during menopause play a hormonal factors, genetic and psychosocial [12,13]. It is believed that the tendency to depression are influenced by changes in hormonal levels. Estrogen deficiency reduces the concentration and activity of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and catecholamines. This causes a decrease in the drive and mood. There is also no stimulation of estrogen receptors within the limbic system responsible for the regulation of emotional behavior (eg. contentment) [8].

Bielawska-Batorowicz [14] reported that the quality of life of women during menopause definitely affect her personality traits, the level of fear experienced, the level of self-esteem and the type style and peeled strategy in the fight against the disease. Also plays a crucial self-acceptance, which is faith and trust in yourself. It not without significance is also a team of judgments and opinions, which I rise lifelong about themselves and posture in relation to itself.

Individual attitude affects mood, determines the range of personal and social behavior. However, generated ideas about his own person may be subject to continuous transformation.

According to The problem [15] throughout life, most people experience problems with self-esteem, constantly striving for strengthening and confirmation. Self-esteem can be high or low, but also a certain or uncertain. About how a woman feels with itself is not determined by the amount of self-esteem but her confidence. The greater conviction as to its value, the greater the resistance to the turbulence experienced during menopause.

Given these factors, you can create the following list of types of self-esteem: high sure high uncertain and a low sure and low uncertain.

The higher and more certain level of self-esteem, the easier it is to cope with the upcoming changes, it is also more resistant to adverse stimuli.

Increasing the quality of life, taking hormonal changes are in this situation, a much smaller impact on the perception of self. In a comfortable position, there are people with low but stable self-esteem. For these people, even minor setback lowers mood, but also gives a sense of confidence.

In the preferred situation, there are also women who have some, but low self-esteem. Such an attitude ensures certainty, even if it is not associated with anything pleasant. In the worst position are women with a high, precarious and unstable self-esteem. These are people exposed to the need for continuous confirmation of self-worth. They have an increased sensitivity to the opinion of environment and changes with age. They are characterized by increased volatility of mood, significant vulnerability to stress and depression [15].

For information on how to respond to the ongoing changes in menopause, they are also driven by personality traits.

People open to the outside and introverted see the world differently, they use different ways of coping with difficult situations.

Study the relationship between personality traits and the way of coping with menopause conducted Bielawska-Batorowicz [14]. Obtained by it results show that women react intensely to stimuli tending to maintain a long-term affect.

The results indicate that high reactivity and neuroticism women correlate positively with one experiences frequency and intensity of menopausal symptoms. Also, women with a high degree of reactivity, that in the struggle with stress use a style based on emotions and avoidance, perceived menopause and the symptoms associated with it, as the experience of a pejorative.

In other studies the quality of life of women highlights the indisputable role of social support and its positive impact on the alleviation of menopausal symptoms experienced [16].

Social support disease is an important element in the healing process, as well as protect against the disease. The main components of social support are caring, trust and care and create a sense of security, care and belonging, which determines the growth of self-supported person [17].

With the support of emotional easier to get rid of tension and negative feelings as well as to express their fears and concerns. Appropriate behavior support person triggers a sense of hope, strength and faith [18].

An invaluable role at this time has the support obtained from the nearest person. The decrease in hormones causes a decrease in sexual interest. During sex women feel pain, there are disturbances in the field of libido, sexual arousal and orgasm disorders.

According to Basson and others [19] HSDD talking about the situation of loss of libido as a consequence leading to stress and difficulties of human relationships. But Sparrow [20] points out that closeness, understanding and acceptance of the relationship partner

and sexual it is far more important for a satisfying sex life than age and related indisposition.

Human sexuality is a sphere of life having the indispensable relationship with feelings, emotions, feeling of pleasure and excitement and Bielawska-Batorowicz and others [14] points out, that the relationship between self-esteem and extraversion is a strong determinant of sexual attractiveness.

While Lauman [21] demonstrates that compounds based on mutual care and effective, clear communication of sexual needs are subject to a much lower risk of sexual dysfunction translate into quality level of mutual relations.

Sek [22] points out, that this support has the same awareness of the proximity of the other person, sense of acceptance and affection received from the partner.

Another factor determining the quality of life of menopausal women is owned by the level of emotional intelligence.

Emotions are an integral part of our existence, However, only the ability to manage their own emotions will give you a sense of power and control over their own lives [20].

In 2009 Bauld and Brown [23] investigated the relationship between psychosocial factors and emotional intelligence in perimenopausal women. The results demonstrated a correlation between high emotional intelligence quotient EI (ang. Emotional intelligence) and higher personal competence [5]. It was found that this group had higher levels of self-awareness, better assessment of their capabilities, He showed control of their own emotional states and characterized by the ability to cope with stress. Manifested more effective in setting goals and implementing strategies of self-regulation, oriented behavior intentional. It highlighted the fact that women with low EI showed a much lower rate adaptive.

Although as reported by Day [24], vegetative symptoms and psychological discomfort underestimate the quality of life of women, However, this competence within the psychological and social help to the vast improvement.

Each stress impairs mental balance, associated with experiencing unpleasant emotion [24]. Dealing with stress in the period of the disease is a very complex process. It determines the source of stress, its duration and intensity, as well as the kind of personality and human skills.

The quality of life during menopause determined largely styles used in the struggle with the stress of the disease. Each of them is a feature of personality, complex behaviors used in a situation of stress. It is a collection of patterns schematic, used by a person in difficult

situations.

The confrontation with the stressful situation can take various forms. We can talk about style based on the task whose main objective is to remove the causes of stress.

Style based on emotions, whose purpose is to discharge the voltage and style based on avoiding consisting in taking action or alternative search company [25].

There are many methods available to adapt to a stressful situation, and their effectiveness varies widely.

There is no universal recipe for effective elimination of stress. Dealing with a difficult situation is to change the situation for the better, by modifying their own behavior and the environment, as well as the mastery of emotion to it from spinning out of control, nie załamaly odporności psychicznej i nie wpłynęły destrukcyjnie na relacje społeczne [25].

To improve the quality of life and eliminate stress factors, women to reach for a large amount of strategy, with their choice depending on the personal characteristics of the selected unit.

One strategy is to bring the confrontation by acceding to solve the problem, seeking information and support. Another way to defuse tension is laughter, overeating, sex, relaxation exercises, music, scream or fight, but also the use of psychoactive substances. A common strategy is also to avoid stressful situations by distancing to the problem, escape into sleep or denial. A common strategy is also to avoid stressful situations by distancing to the problem, escape into sleep or denial. Another way is to use a stressful situation to self-destruct, samoponizania and devalue its people and achievements.

You can also try to control their own emotions, or not to give a negative impulses. You can also seek the positive reevaluation experienced stimuli, accepting the loss and come to terms with his fate. The way to combat stress is also seeking support from others, seek good advice or forgotten [26].

As you can see, there are no universal strategies, not all of them contribute to solving the problem, and some of them may even act destructively.

The key issue when dealing with a difficult situation is the correct assessment of the situation and fit an appropriate strategy.

To improve the quality of life during menopause it will be necessary to change existing habits. These include quitting smoking as a factor triggering premature menopause, osteoporosis and heart disease, and lung. Also helps to limit alcohol and coffee, as factors causing insomnia, anxiety and hot flashes. Changing eating habits to a diet rich in fruits, vegetables, omega 6 and 3, and calcium and vitamin D reduces the risk of osteoporosis

and heart disease [27].

It is also recommended keeping an active lifestyle based on physical exercise, tailored to the age and capabilities of the unit and the corresponding strengthening of the abdominal muscles and pelvic floor as prevention of stress urinary incontinence and pelvic organ prolapse improve [28].

Stress is a common part of our everyday life. How can we reduce its impact largely depends on us. It is important to realize that this is not the stress, but our response to stress shapes the quality of our lives.

In a study conducted by the Saxon-Obad, and others [29] drew attention to the relationship between mature and integrated identity of the entity, quality of life and acceptance of menopausal symptoms.

According to the literature, a mature and integrated identity is characterized by the ability of a person to adequately contact with itself, its own processes somatic-mental. It is also the competence to properly communicate to people the image of their own identity and integrity, as well as the right to a person how to react in the framework of contacts. The high degree of mature identity ensures better tolerance to situations ambivalent and frustrating. It also allows an increase in awareness of learning and respecting their needs and expectations [30].

The results confirm the validity of the above theories have noted Saxon-Obad, and others [29] saying, that the more mature and integrated identity, the lower the frequency and intensity of symptoms experienced by women during menopause.

The results also confirm the assumption, that stable personality traits in order to minimize the negative stimuli. There was also a link between the perception of one's own body, the degree of acceptance and the incidence of vasomotor symptoms and psychiatric symptoms. It was also shown a relationship between the ability to exercise control over their own emotions and the way to deal with the symptoms of menopause.

References:

1. Grady D. Clinical practice. Management of menopausal symptoms. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 2006; 355, 2338–2247.
2. Glazer G., Zeller R., Delumba L. et al The Ohio Midlife Women's Study. *Health Care Women Int*, 2002; 2, 612–630.
3. Mącik D., Ziółkowska P. Sytuacje postrzeganej utraty kobiecości: menopauza, mastektomia – zmiany w obrazie siebie jako kobiety. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*, 2012; 6, 456–462.
4. Bloch A. Self-awareness during the menopause. *Maturitas*, 2002; 41, 61–8.
5. Extremera N., Fernandez-Berrocal P. Relation of perceived emotional intelligence and health related quality of life of middle-aged woman. *Psychological Reports*, 2002; 91, 47–59.

6. Santoro N.F., Skalnik-Wikiel M.E. Leczenie zaburzeń nastroju i pamięci w okresie menopauzy. *Ginekologia po Dyplomie*, 2015; 17, 1, 95, 13–17.
7. Buster J.E. Seks a pięćdziesięciolatka: jak na nowo czerpać satysfakcję. *Ginekologia po Dyplomie*, 2012; 14, 5, 81, 70–78.
8. Bręborowicz G. (red.). *Położnictwo i Ginekologia*. Warszawa: PZWL, 2006;
9. Seedat S., Sott K.M., Angermeyer M.C. et al. Cross national associations between gender and mental disorders in the World Health Organization World Mental Surveys. *This Month in Archives of General Psychiatry*, 2009; 66, 7, 785–795.
10. Geerlings M.I., Schoevers R.A., Beekman A.T. et al. Depression and risk cognitive decline and Alzheimer's disease. Results of two prospective community-based studies in The Netherlands. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 2000; 176, 568–575.
11. Henderson V.W., Guthrie J.R., Dudley E.C., Burger H.C., Dennerstein L. Estrogen exposures and memory at midlife: a population-based study of women. *Neurology*, 2003; 60, 8, 1369–1371.
12. Baldwin D.S., Hirschfeld R. *Depresja*. Wydawnictwo Medyczne Via Medica. Gdańsk, 2001;
13. Lipińska-Szałek A., Sobczuk A., Pertyński T., Stetkiewicz T., Szymczak W. Wpływ czynników biologicznych i psychospołecznych na psychiczne aspekty okresu okołomenopauzalnego. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*, 2003; 6, 55–61.
14. Bielawska-Batorowicz E. Temperament, osobowość i styl radzenia sobie ze stresem a częstość i intensywność objawów menopauzalnych. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*, 2007; 2, 70–76.
15. Sęk H. *Wprowadzenie do psychologii klinicznej. Wykłady z psychologii*, 5. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe Scholar, 2001;
16. Wojciszke B. *Człowiek wśród ludzi. Zarys psychologii społecznej (t.8)*. Warszawa : Wydawnictwo Naukowe Scholar, 2002;
17. Bańka A. (red.). *Psychologia jakości życia*. Poznań: Stowarzyszenie psychologia i Architektura, 2005;
18. Kuryłowicz J. *Radzenie sobie z własną chorobą. Badanie psychologiczne pacjentów zespołem bólowym korzeniowym*. Lublin: Verba, 2006;
19. Basson R., Berman J., Burnett A., et al. Report of the international consensus development conference on female sexual dysfunction: definitions and classifications. *The Journal of Urology*, 2000; 163, 3, 888–893.
20. Wróbel B. Wyniki badania wybranych cech seksualności kobiet w związku małżeńskim. *Ginekologia Polska*, 2008; 79, 2, 81–160.
21. Lauman E., Nicolosi A., Glasser D., et al. Sexual problems among women and men aged 40–80: prevalence and correlates identified in the global study of Sexual Attitudes and behaviors. *International Journal of Impotence Research's Latest Table of Contents*, 2005; 17, 39–57.
22. Sęk H. Wsparcie społeczne jako kategoria zasobów. W: *Zasoby osobiste i społeczne sprzyjające zdrowiu jednostki (red.) Z. Juszczyński, N. Ogińska-Bulik*, Łódź: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Łódzkiego, 2003;
23. Bauld R., Brown R.F. (). *Stress, psychological distress, menopause symptoms and physical health in women*. *Maturitas*, 2009; 62, 2, 160–165.
24. Day A., Therien D., Carrol S. Predicting psychological health: assessing the incremental validity emotional intelligence beyond personality, type A behavior and daily hassles. *European Journal of Personality*, 2005; 19, 519–536.
25. Trelak J.F. *Psychologia stresu*. Oficyna Wydawnicza Bronta. Bydgoszcz, 2001;
26. Ratajczak Z. *Stres – radzenie – koszty psychologiczne (W:) I Heszen-Niejodek, Ratajczak Z. (red.) Człowiek w sytuacji stresu. Problemy teoretyczne i metodologiczne*. Katowice: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Śląskiego, 2000; 44–46.
27. Dąbrowska J., Naworska B., Dąbrowska-Galas M., Skrzypulec-Plinta V. The role of physical activity in menopause. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*, 2012; 6, 445–448.
28. Paszkowski T., Radomański T. W 60 rocznicę opracowania podstaw naukowych rehabilitacji mięśni dna miednicy. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*, 2008; 12, 103–6.
29. Sakson-Obada O., Wycisk J. The body self and the frequency, intensity and acceptance of menopausal symptoms. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*, 2015; 14, 2, 82–89.
30. Drzewicki M. (red.). *Cielesność, płciowość, seksualność*. Kielce: Jedność, 2000;

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